

Original Article

Analysis of Tool Geometry and Hole Quality Effects on Drilling Carbon-Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites Using ANSYS

¹David Johnson and ²Clara Smith

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Massachusetts Institute of Technology,
USA

²Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of Toronto, Canada

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850874>

Abstract: This study focused on the analysis of the effect of tool geometry and hole quality on drilling carbon-fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite using ANSYS. The experiment was conducted on computer numerical control machine (CNC) using high speed steel (HSS) twist drill bit and HSS-COBALT drill type. Taguchi L9 orthogonal array was used for the optimization analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the most significant control factors affecting the drilling process. The machining parameters involving tool type, point angle, spindle speed and feed rate were selected as control factors. While the dependable variables on workpiece were cutting force, stress and strain. The main interaction effect of the input variables on the predicted responses was investigated. The ANOVA/F-test results for cutting force with the contribution of each machining parameters revealed that the cutting speed was the dominant factor influencing cutting force developed with a contribution of 57 percent, The second factor affecting cutting force developed was point angle with a contribution of 5.7 percent, while feed rate had the least effect on cutting force developed where its contribution of 1.4 percent. Based on the results observed, the optimal machining parameters that produced minimum stress was observed with HSSCOBALT drill at 118 degrees of point angle, 300 mm/min of feed and 500 rpm of speed. Also from Taguchi results, the optimal combination of process parameters to obtain maximum strain with HSS drill, 135 degrees of point angle, and 300 mm/min of feed and 1500 rpm of speed produced the optimal drilling condition for CFRC polymer within the scope of this research work.

Keywords: ANOVA, ANSYS, CFRC polymer, Drilling parameters, Tool Geometry.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are increasingly used in various fields of endeavors, such as aeronautics, maritime, and automobile industries. The assembly of different aircrafts structures requires machining of different component parts. Drilling of thick component plates have posed some significant challenges during drilling operations because of the fast rise of stress and strain induced in the work piece material by cutting force. This causes defects

Original Article

at the hole entry, exit total strain were simulated and analyzed using ANSYS and finally the obtained results were optimized by using single objective optimization technique known as Taguchi robust method.

Yingying *et al.* (2016) investigated the effect of drilling parameters and tool geometry on drilling performance in drilling carbon fibre–reinforced plastic/ titanium alloy stacks. An experimental study on drilling of carbon fibre–reinforced plastic/titanium alloy was conducted using three kinds of drills to investigate the cutting process. Their research was mainly focused on the drilling forces, drilling temperatures, chips, and delamination area with respect to the cutting parameters and tool geometries. . The influence of drilling parameters and tool geometries was analysed and the conclusions were drawn that the proper selection of drilling parameters and drill geometries could lead to better whole quality

Pravin *et al.* (2017) performed modeling and simulation of drilling process in Ti-6Al-4V, Al6061 using Deform-3D software. They stated that drilling is an important process for the manufacturing of any products. In their research work the drilling process was carried out by finite element modeling and simulated with the help of DEFORM-3D software. The composite alloy material Ti-6Al-4V and Al6061 was drilled to obtain the desired hole using the diamond drill bit. They stated that the titanium alloy which is widely used in the field of biomedical applications, whereas the Al6061 aluminium alloy is mostly applicable in automotive and aerospace industries. The simulation obtained showed that Ti-6Al-4V had higher stresses and temperature distribution than Al6061 material, which may possibly be an effect of physical properties of Ti-6Al-4V material.

Manoj *et al.* (2019) carried out finite element stress analysis of drill bit in ANSYS. They stated that drilling is a slicing procedure that utilizes a boring device to reduce or amplify a gap of round about move-location in strong substances. Their study aimed at investigating the dull tool essentially with help of Finite factor exam. Right off the bat the dull device was displayed in Catia and the equal was added into the ANSYS for modular and auxiliary exam of present Tungsten carbide device and D2 metallic cloth tool. The result from their examination showed that the explicit condition the D2 metallic material should be taken into consideration for making drill holes.

Madhavan and Balasivanadha (2012) conducted an experimental investigation and analysis of thrust force in drilling of carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites using response surface methodology (RSM). Their study reported the effect of thrust force during drilling of 10mm diameter holes in 20mm thick Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic composite laminate using HSS, Solid Carbide (K20) and Polycrystalline Diamond insert drills .The correlation model for drilling parameters considering thrust force and Response surface Methodology (RSM) revealed that it was good for thrust force prediction. The investigation revealed that the type of drill geometry affects the thrust force significantly followed by the feed rate and the speed.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study were:

- i To analyses the effect of drilling parameters on cutting force in CNC drilling of carbon-fibre reinforced composite (CFRC) polymer.
- ii To analyses the effect of induced stress and strain on whole quality (delamination) when drilling CFRC polymer.
- iii To determine optimal machining parameters (feed, spindle speed and cutting force) for the drilling operation of CFRC polymer.

Original Article

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The material of the work piece used in carrying out this study is the carbon-fibre reinforced polymer composite (coir-bagasse hybrid polyester) composite. For drilling, the composite specimen was cut in square shape of 150mm by 150mm with thickness of 10mm. The experimental specimen (workpiece) is a soft material which has good mechanical and metallurgical properties.

The machining tool used was the High-Speed Steel tool drill bit (HSS) and HSS Cobalt tool single point cutting tool. Series of experiments were made by HSS and HSS Cobalt type twisted drills and each with three different point angles of 118°, 130°, and 135° respectively

The material properties of carbon-fibre reinforced polymer composite work-piece and the drilling tool specifications are presented in table 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1 Material Carbon-Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite Work-Piece.

Tensile Strength	600 MPa
Fibre Volume	50%
Modulus of Elasticity	70 GPa

Properties	Value
Thermal Coefficient of Expansion	2.1 x 10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹
Compressive Strength	570 MPa
Density	1.6 g/cm ³
Shear Modulus	5 GPa
Shear Strength	90 MPa

(Source: Shim *et al.*, 2002)

Table 2 Geometric Variables of the Machining Tool

Parameter	Value
Overall Length of tool (mm)	700
Shank diameter (mm)	50
Flute length (mm)	210
Number of flute	2
Flute diameter (mm)	50
Helix angle (degree)	75°

(Shim *et al.*, 2002)

2.2 Methods I

The Taguchi method L9 orthogonal array was applied to design of experiment in this research work since the control factors are more than two. This method explores the concept of quadratic quality loss function and uses a statistical measure of performance called signal to noise (S/N) ratio (Akhyar *et al.*, 2008). **II**

Original Article

The analysis of variance (ANOVA)/F-test was used to test the significance between the simulated and experimental results. The F-test is best used in cases where the hypothesis means of a normally distributed population all have the same standard deviation.

2.3 Drilling process analysis

Optimal drilling performance cannot be actualized without taking the following drilling parameters into consideration; Cutting parameters (spindle speed and axial feed), cutting conditions (dry, with coolant or lubricant), work-piece characteristics (material, geometry, structure etc.), fixturing configuration and the machine tool are to be considered as well in the drilling process analysis.

Ignoring the feed, the cutting speed at the periphery can be expressed as:

$$V = \pi . D . n \tag{1}$$

Where D is the drill diameter. The axial feed, often simply referred to as “feed” is the tool advancement per revolution along its cutting path in mm/rev. The feed rate (or axial speed) is the speed at which the tool advances into the part in (mm/min), and is related to f through the spindle speed n by:

$$f_r = f . n \tag{2}$$

The feed per tooth, ft (mm/rev) depends on axial feed (f) and the number of flutes N [-], and is used to calculate the depth of cut (tc).

$$f_r = \frac{f}{N} \tag{3}$$

The feed rate (axial speed) is the input parameter provided to the machine tool.

equations 5 to 7 (Johnson & Cook’s,1983).

$$\sigma = (A + B\varepsilon_p^n [1 + C \ln(\dot{\varepsilon}^*)])[1 - (T^*)^m]$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = A + B(\varepsilon^{pl})^n \left[1 + C \ln \frac{\dot{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right] \left[1 - \frac{T - T_r}{T_m - T_r} \right]^m$$

$$T^* = \begin{cases} 0; T < T_{room} \\ (T - T_{room}) / (T_{mslt} - T_{room}); T_{room} \leq T \leq T_{mslt} \\ 1; T > T_{mslt} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

The cutting force can be estimated using the equation specified by Madhavan & Balasivanadha, (2012).

$$Cutting\ Force = Pe \times 60 \times 10^3 \times Coefficient\ of\ Efficiency$$

$$= Feed \times Spindle\ Cutting\ Speed \times \cos \alpha$$

Where,
 Pe = Power of machine (2.238kW)
 Coefficient of Efficiency = 0.75

α = Point angle

The analysis of hole quality (delamination) in terms of stresses and strains are shown in

$$\tag{5} \tag{6}$$

(Johnson & Cook’s ,1983).

Properly selection of the parameter levels to maximize optimal performance was achieved from Taguchi techniques and signal to noise ratio (S/N)

Summarized the levels from equations. 8, 9 & 10 respectively.

Nalbant et al. (2007)

Original Article

(i) The nominal-the-better (NB)

$$\frac{S}{N_T} = 10 * \log \left(\frac{\bar{y}^2}{s^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

(ii) Larger-The-Better (LB)

$$\frac{S}{N_L} = -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{y} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y^{i2}} \right) \quad (9)$$

(iii) The smaller-the-better (SB)

$$\frac{S}{N} = -10 * \log \left(\frac{1}{y} \sum_{i=1}^n y^{i2} \right) \quad (10)$$

But the larger the better was chosen for this research work.

Degree of Freedom(DOF)

$$(11)$$

$$\square \quad \square \square L \quad \square 1 \square x P \quad \square \square 1$$

2.4 Completely Randomized Design (CRD).

Completely randomized design is a basic single factor design, in this design the treatment (response parameters) are assigned completely at random so that each experimental unit has the same chance of receiving any one treatment. But CRD is appropriate only when the experimental material is homogeneous. CRD is utilised to analyse data when the following conditions are needed;

- i. To determine whether the difference between the group means are statistically significant.
- ii. To examine the group means. iii. To compare the group means. iv. To determine how well the model fits a given set of data.
- v. To determine if your model fits the assumption of your data

$$\text{Grand Mean } G = \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2 + \mu_3 + \dots + \mu_n}{n} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Sum of Squares (SS)} = \sum_{i=0}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \quad (13)$$

Where: $X_i = i^{th}$ term

$\bar{X}$ = Grand mean

Original Article

$$SS_{total} = \sum x^2 - CF \tag{14}$$

$$Treatment\ SS = \sum \frac{T^2}{r} = \frac{T_1^2}{r_1} + \frac{T_2^2}{r_2} + \frac{T_3^2}{r_3} \dots \frac{T_{n+1}^2}{r_{n+1}} - CF \tag{15}$$

$$Correction\ factor\ (C.F) = \frac{G^2}{n} \tag{16}$$

$$Means\ Square\ error\ (MSE) = \frac{SS\ Error}{Df\ Error}$$

F – Calculated

$$= \frac{Means\ Square\ treatment\ (MST)}{means\ Square\ error\ (MSE)} \tag{18}$$

(17)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The carbon fibre reinforced composite (CFRC) polymer (workpiece Model) was prepared and geometry were after meshing generated, the equivalent cutting force ,stresses and strains was analyzed and simulated using Ansys. The results of these with HSS & HSS-Cobalt drill type at different speed levels, tool point angle, and feed rate engaged at 500rpm (261.6 m/sec) spindle speed. Eighteen holes were examined i.e 18 experimental runs and the results presented in table 3.

Figure 1 Initial Geometry before Meshing

Original Article

Figure 2 Geometry after Meshing

Table 3: Experimental Design Using L9 Orthogonal Array and Results.

								Tool
Geometry								
Exp.	Feed rate	Spindle	Cutting	Stress	Strain			
No	Drill Type	Pointangle	(mm/min)	speed (rpm)	Force	(N)	((xN/m 10 ⁹ 2))	
(°)								
1	HSS	118	100	500	4.290	8.652	0.8627	
2	HSS	118	200	1000	1.073	2.227	1.2091	
3	HSS	118	300	1500	0.476	2.049	1.4171	
4	HSS	130	100	1500	1.045	8.652	1.0091	
5	HSS	130	200	500	1.567	5.301	1.2091	
6	HSS	130	300	1000	0.226	3.106	1.4171	
7	HSS	135	100	1000	1.424	7.713	1.2784	
8	HSS	135	200	1500	0.475	4.372	1.2784	
9	HSS	135	300	500	0.950	2.667	1.5154	
10	HSS	118	100	500	4.576	7.713	1.2784	
CO								
11	HSS	118	200	1000	1.144	1.667	1.5154	
CO								
12	HSS	118	300	1500	1.671	1.349	1.2704	
CO								
13	HSS	130	100	1500	1.114	7.713	1.2784	
CO								
14	HSS	130	200	500	1.671	1.665	1.5095	
CO								
15	HSS	130	300	1000	0.557	1.350	1.5154	

Original Article

CO							
16	HSS	135	100	1000	1.519	7.521	1.2784
18		0.923	0.917	0.920		1.2784	

Figure 3: Cutting Force of the Drill Tools

CO							
17	HSS	135	200	1500	0.506	4.001	1.3154
CO							
18	HSS	135	300	500	1.013	2.227	1.2784
CO							

High speed steel (HSS);High Speed Steel Cobalt(HSS-Cobalt)

Table 3. reveals the results of the cutting force of the drill tools on the carbon-fibre reinforced composite polymer work-piece for the nine (9) runs of experiments. The figure showed that the 10th experiment using HSS-COBALT drill tool (experiment with point angle 118 degrees, feed rate at 100mm/min.

Table 4: Experimental results for signal ratio on cutting force

2				1.071	1.091	1.081		4.2255	
3				1.039	1.142	1.091		6.6509	
4				1.047	1.056	1.046		4.5097	
5				1.574	1.559	1.567		2.6153	
6				0.228	0.234	0.231		1.1761	
7				1.458	1.446	1.452		9.1196	
8				0.485	1.471	0.978		0.6281	
9				0.855	0.822	0.839		5.1927	
10	4.576	4.497	4.537	1.2784					
11	1.148	1.150	1.149	0.4154					
12	1.671	0.509	1.090	1.2703					
13	1.116	1.120	1.118	1.2784					
14	0.584	0.641	0.613	1.5095					
15	0.647	0.900	0.774	0.3152					
16	1.023	1.041	1.032	1.2784	17	0.259	0.265	0.262	1.3251

Original Article

Figure 4: Equivalent Stress Developed on Drilled Polymer Workpiece

Figure 5: Equivalent Strain Developed on Drilled Polymer Workpiece

Figure 6: Stress Developed Against Cutting Force of HSS Drill Tool and HSS-Cobalt

Figure 7: Scatter Plots of the Experimental and Predicted Values of Cutting Force on HSS and HSS-Cobalt Tool

3.1 Optimization of Result

The obtained results of equivalent stresses, strain and cutting force were optimized using single objective optimization tool called Taguchi method while Minitab16 was used for analyzing the experimental data.

Original Article

Figure 8: Main Effects Plots of Means for cutting Force Developed

The significant relationship between the experimental and simulated results of the experiment was done using ANOVA analysis (Complete randomized design techniques).

- (i) From cutting force, the F-value calculated 3.02 was less than the F-value 4.35 tabulated at 5% confidence level which shows there was insignificant difference between the interactions of the control machining parameters used during experiment.
- (ii) From equivalent Stress, the F-value calculated 186.7 was greater than the F-value 4.38 tabulated at 5% confidence level which shows that there was significance difference between the machining parameters used in the drilling process.
- (iii) From equivalent Strain, the F-value calculated 1.79 was less than the F-value 4.38 tabulated at 5% confidence level which shows that there was insignificant difference between the machining parameters used in the drilling operation of CFRC polymer. (iv)

4. CONCLUSION

The first objectives of this study which was to evaluate the effect of drilling parameters and tool geometry on cutting force in CNC drilling of carbon-fibre reinforced polymer composite was achieved from the ANSYS computer simulation as presented in Figure 1 which revealed using HSS-COBALT drill tool (10th experiment with point angle 118 degrees, feed rate at 100mm/min. and spindle speed at 500rpm) produced the greatest cutting force at 4.578N when compared HSS tool (1st experiment with point angle 118^o, feed rate 100mm/min, and spindle speed 500rpm) at 4.290N.

The second objective which was to determine an optimal machining parameter for the drilling operation of carbon-fibre reinforced polymer composite that enhances its quality and productivity. The ANOVA analysis results for signal to Noise ratio on cutting force with the contribution of each machining parameters in decreasing order are cutting speed with contribution of 57.8%, point angle with contribution of 5.7%, feed rate with contribution of 1.4%.

- i. The tool geometry and cutting parameter that produces optimal results of the equivalent cutting force, stress and equivalent elastic strain exerted by the drilling tool on the work piece during a machining have been

Original Article

identified and should be adopted to control the tool deflection and improves hole quality integrity and productivity.

ii. This research can be extended by investigating the use of different diameter of drills and helix angles to improve productivity and performance when drilling CFRC Polymer.

REFERENCES

- Akhyars, G., Horon, C.H.C., Ghani, J.A. (2008) Application of Taguchi Method in the optimization of turning parameters for surface roughness. *International journal of Science Engineering and Technology*, 1(3) 60-66
- Amarnath, R. M. & Subhash, R. J. (2015). Optimization of Drilling Process Parameters: A Review. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, 3(2), 21-33.
- Ch.Dipak, K., Ch.Maheswara, R., Bindhu, N. V., Vara, P. R. (2019). Numerical Simulation and Optimization of Drilling Process Parameters Using ANSYS and Taguchi Method. *A Journal of Composition Theory*, 12 (8), 339-345.
- Chen, M., Liu, G. & Zhang, X. (2007). Optimization Studies on Hole-Making Tools for High-Performance Cutting Austenitic Stainless Steel. *Machining Science and Technology*, 11(2), 183–200.
- Dandekar, C. R., & Shin, Y. C. (2012). Modeling of machining of composite materials: A review. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 57(1), 102-121.
- Feito, N., Díaz-Álvarez, J., Cantero, J. L., & Miguélez, M. H. (2015). Influence of Special Tool Geometry in Drilling Woven CFRPs Materials. *Materials. Procedia Engineering* 132(2015) 632-638.
- Islam, S. E. M. S. (2010) Drilling of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic Composites. Ph.D Thesis, School of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Birmingham.
- Ismail, S. O., Dhakal, H. N., Popov, I., & Beaugrand, J. (2016c). Comprehensive study on machinability of sustainable and conventional fibre reinforced polymer composites. *Engineering Science and Technology, An international Journal*, 19(4), 2043-2052.
- Johnson, G.R. & Cook, W.H. (1983) A constitutive model and data for metals subjected to large strains high strain rates and high temperatures. In Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Ballistics, Hague.
- Kılıçkap, E. (2010). Optimization of Cutting Parameters on Delamination Based on Taguchi Method During Drilling of GFRP Composite. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(8), 6116-6122.
- Kilickap, E. & Huseyinoglu, M. (2010). Selection of Optimum Drilling Parameters on Burr Height Using Response Surface Methodology and Genetic Algorithm in Drilling of AISI 30 Stainless Steel. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 25(10), 1068–1076.

Original Article

- Krishnaraj, V., Vijayarangan, S. & Ramesh, K. A. (2007). Effect of Drilling Parameters on Mechanical Strength in Drilling Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastic. *International Journal of Computer Applications in Technology*, 28 (1), 87-93.
- Kuo, C., Chun, L. & Zhang, W. (2014). The Effect of Cutting Speed and Feed Rate on Hole Surface Integrity in Single-Shot Drilling of Metallic Composite Stacks. *Procedia CIRP*, 405-410.
- Kuram, E., Ozcelik, B., Demirbas, E., SSik, E., & Tansel, I. N. (2011). Evaluation of New Vegetable-Based Cutting Fluids on Thrust Force and Surface Roughness in Drilling of AISI 304 using Taguchi method. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 26(9), 1136-1146.
- Latha B., Senthilkumar,V.S. & Palanikumar, (2011). Modeling and Optimization of Process Parameter for Delamination in Drilling GFRP Composites. *Machining Science and Technology*, 15(2), 172–191.
- Liu D.F, Tang, Y .J, & Cong, W .L. (2012) A review of mechanical drilling for composite Laminates. *Compos Struct*, 94:1265–79
- Mahdi, M. & Zhang, L. (2001). A Finite Element Model for the Orthogonal Cutting of FibreReinforced Composite Materials. *J Mater Process Technol*, 113-115.
- Madhavan, S. & Balasivanadha, S. P. (2012). Experimental Investigation and Analysis of Thrust Force in Drilling of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic Composites using Response Surface Methodology. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)*, 12 (4), 2719-2723.
- Manoj, G., Reddy, D., Pinakapani, R., K. Jagadeesh, M. S., & Hanumantha, R. Y. V. (2019). Finite Element Stress Analysis of Drill Bit in ANSYS. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE)*. 8(7), 463-467.
- Meena, A. & Mansori, M. (2011). Study of Dry and Minimum Quantity Lubrication Drilling of Novel Austempered Ductile Iron for Automotive Applications. *Wear*, 271, 24122416.
- Ming-Yi, C. (2017). An Experimental Investigation into Tool Wear in Micro-drilling of Aluminium, Aluminium/Copper Metal Alloys and Carbon Fibre Reinforced Composites. *Masters' Degree Thesis, College of Engineering, Design and Physical Sciences Brunel University London*.
- Mishra, B.P., Mishra,D., & Pandal, P(2018): A review, *International Journal of Advanced Mechanical Engineering Production Engineering Department, Veer SurendraSai University of Technology, Burla*, 8(1),153-172.
- Nalbant, M.; Gokkaya, H.; and Sur, G. (2007) “Application of Taguchi method in the optimization of cutting parameters for surface roughness in turning”, *Materials and design*, 28, 1379- 1385.

Original Article

- Ozcelik, B. & Bagci, E. (2006). Experimental and Numerical Studies on the Determination of Twist Drill Temperature in Dry Drilling: A New Approach. *Materials and Design*, 27, 629–636.
- Pawar, P., Ballav R., & Kumar A. (2016). Finite Element Method Broach Tool Drilling Analysis Using Explicit Dynamics ANSYS. *International Journal of Modern Manufacturing Technologies*, 8(2), 54-60.
- Pravin, P., Raj, B., & Amaresh, K. (2017). Modeling and Simulation of Drilling Process in Ti-6Al-4V, Al6061 Using Deform-3D Software. *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*. 10(3) 137-142.
- Prince, K. D. & Titariya, V. K. (2018). Modeling & Simulation of the Drilling Cutter by using Finite Element Method. *IJSRD - International Journal for Scientific Research & Development*, 5(12), 71-76.
- Saravana, M., Kumar, S., Bharani, K. S., Joe, P. G., Prabakaran, P. R., & Ebenezer, S. P. (2020). Optimization of Machining Parameter in Drilling of Coir-Bagasse Natural Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites. *International journal of scientific & technology research*, 9(1), 4250-4255.
- Shim, H., Seo, M. & Park, S. (2002). Thermal Conductivity and Mechanical Properties of Various Cross-Section Types Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Composites. *Journal of Materials Science*, 37(9) 1881-1885.
- Shivani, L. P., Singh, P. & Alok, Y. (2019). Modelling & Analysis of Drill Bit with different Materials. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 7(34), 194-199.
- Sudha J., Sampathkumar S. & Vijaya A, (2009). AE Waveform Analysis of Delamination in GFRP Composite Materials during Drilling. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(1) 63-66.
- Teti, R. (2002). Machining of Composite Materials. *Annals of the CIRP*, 51(2), 611-634,
- Tsao, C. C., & Hocheng, H. (2004). Taguchi analysis of delamination associated with various drill bits in drilling of composite material. *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 44(10), 1085-1090.
- Tsao, C. C. & Hocheng, H. (2007). Effect of Tool Wear on Delamination in Drilling Composite Materials. *International Journal of Mechanical Science*, 49(8), 983-988.
- Tsao, C. C. (2008). Prediction of Thrust Force of Step Drill in Drilling Composite Material by Taguchi Method and Radial Basis Function Network. *International Journal of Advance Manufacturing Technology*, 36(9), 11-18.
- Weiyang, X., Yanping, Z. & Juan, J. (2018). Mechanical Model for Oblique Hole Drilling and Bit Life Analysis in Conventional Design. *Advances in Intelligent Systems Research*, 163(8), 555-561.

Original Article

Yingying W., Qinglong A., Weiwei, M., & Ming, C. (2016). Effect of Drilling Parameters and Tool Geometry on Drilling Performance in Drilling Carbon Fibre–Reinforced Plastic/ Titanium Alloy Stacks. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, 8(9), 1–16.